

The image shows two hands, one on the left and one on the right, gripping white gymnastic rings. The hands are wrapped in white athletic tape, and each hand has a red wristband. The background is black, making the white rings and tape stand out. The text is centered in the upper half of the image.

More than a voice: White Paper on Being Athlete Centred

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**With adapted content from Athlete-centred sport. Discussion paper, by AthletesCAN, 1994. Copyright 1994.*

**** This document was originally developed in 2021 for the Commonwealth Games Federation Athletes Advisory Commission.**

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commonwealth sport

INTRODUCTION

Athletes are the only key stakeholders in the sport system that are both the consumer and producer of sports. They are both the reason for the existence of any sport entity and yet they also require support to be successful. Ideally, all extensions of the sport system should provide a holistically positive experience for the athlete. In so doing, the success of athletes provides a reciprocal benefit to the various sport entities.

For a major multi-sport games like the Commonwealth Games, its success is integral to the success of the Commonwealth Games Federation (CGF). Athletes play a vital role in the success of the Games, as well as the years in between, for both the Commonwealth Games Associations (CGA) and the CGF. From the moment an athlete is selected to represent their country for the Games, until they retire, they will always be a Commonwealth Games athlete.

The Commonwealth Games plays an integral role in that journey of a Commonwealth athlete. For some athletes, the Games are their pinnacle sporting moment, and for others it may be a monumental step in their progression as a world class athlete. A positive experience with the Commonwealth Sport Movement, promotes the holistic development of the athlete. Therefore, there is an incumbent responsibility by the entire Commonwealth Sport Movement to ensure a positive experience that fosters excellence for athletes both on the field of play and off.

The mission of the CGF is rooted in being athlete-centred. The CGF's Athlete Advisory Commission (AAC) lauds this mission and hopes other sport organizations will also adopt this philosophy. The purpose of this document is to establish consistency with what it means to be athlete-centred by defining the term, identifying characteristics of an athlete-centred sport system, providing recommendations as to how members of the Commonwealth Sport can take steps to becoming more athlete-centred, and identifying the ways athlete-centredness can be assessed within the Commonwealth Sport Movement.

What is Athlete-Centred?

The term athlete-centred, is abundantly used by coaches, national sport organizations, and multi-sport organizations, with the assumption its meaning is understood and shared by all. This can lead to misunderstandings, resulting in sport organizations meaning well, yet falling short of athlete-centredness aspirations. For example, allowing athletes to voice their opinions is considered to be athlete-centred. This is not the case. To be athlete-centred is both a concept and a process.¹

One of the first known mentions and advocacy for sport systems to be athlete-centred was by Taylor in 1976 in a report on the unification of sport.² However, it was not until 1994, that athlete-centred was first defined by AthletesCAN, the first fully independent organization in the world, developed by athletes to represent the collective voice of all national team athletes.

*The term athlete-centred refers to both a concept and a process, rather than a single action or event. In an athlete-centred sport system, the values, programs, policies, resource allocation and priorities of sport organizations and agencies place primary emphasis on consideration of athletes' needs in a holistic sense and performance goals within that context. Those responsible for leadership and decision-making in sport must include the athlete in both defining the needs and goals and in determining how to meet them; i.e. the athlete should be the active subject in, not the object of, sporting programs.*³

Here within, athlete-centred extends beyond athletes simply having the ability to voice their concerns; rather it is a process which involves having athletes define needs and goals which relate to them and determine how best to meet them; as well as including athletes in the decision-making process. As such, the CGF's AAC fully endorses this definition of what it means for a sport organization to be athlete-centred.

¹ AthletesCAN. (1994). *Athlete-centred sport. Discussion paper*. Retrieved from https://athletescan.com/sites/default/files/images/athlete_centered_sport_-_discussion_paper.pdf

² Taylor, B. (1976). *Report: Unification of Sport*. Ottawa, ON: Committee for the Unification of Sport.

³ AthletesCAN. (1994). *Athlete-centred sport. Discussion paper*. pp.17.

CHARACTERISTICS OF ATHLETE-CENTREDNESS

Athlete-centredness places the interests of athletes at the heart of the organization, respecting and protecting athletes' independence, whereby decisions are made in support of the athlete. The following 10 key attributes of an athlete-centred sport system should be considered in the development of policies and procedures within the CGF and wider Commonwealth Sport Movement.⁴

Accountability

The Commonwealth Sport Movement is accountable to its consumers the athletes, upholding its values of humanity, equality, and destiny. Whereby, all Commonwealth athletes are embraced; fairness, non-discrimination, and inclusion are promoted; and Commonwealth athletes are assisted in realizing their aspirations and ambitions.

Dual Respect

By treating athletes with respect and autonomy, athletes grow in learning the value of respecting others in diverse roles and their ability to offer unique contributions, for the betterment of all.

Empowerment

Athletes gain leadership, problem solving and decision-making skills, enhancing their growth as individuals. With empowerment, the input of elected athletes is both heard and acted upon; athletes can see their contributions in the decision-making process of the organization.

Equity/Fairness

The act of ensuring accessible, equitable, and inclusive opportunities is provided to all Commonwealth athletes.

Excellence

Adequate support is provided to athletes to ensure they can pursue self-actualization both on and off the field of competition.

Extended Responsibility

The CGF recognizes the impact it has on the athletic journey of a Commonwealth athlete. Decisions affecting Commonwealth athletes takes this into consideration, to ensure the experience for the athlete is positive, and one that will keep them involved in sports and the Commonwealth Sport Movement lifelong.

Health

The mental and physical health of all Commonwealth athletes are given the highest priority and safeguarded.

⁴ Adapted from Athlete-centred sport. Discussion paper (p. 18-19), by AthletesCAN, 1994. Copyright 1994 by Ann Peel.

Informed Participation

Commonwealth athletes are given choices and kept aware of potential consequences and trade-offs.

Mutual Support

Meeting objectives, problem solving, and decision-making is recognized as being interdependent of both the athletes and others within the Commonwealth Sport. Whereby, the accomplishments and efforts are shared and celebrated.

Rights

The Commonwealth athlete's rights are clearly defined and outlined, mutually agreed upon, and safeguarded.

THE BENEFITS OF BEING ATHLETE-CENTRED

It is well understood that being athlete-centred leads to excellence in the sport-system and benefits all key stakeholders in the process.⁵ Specifically, some of the benefits Commonwealth Sport can expect to gain from being athlete centred, include but are not limited to:

- Greater awareness, engagement, and commitment to the Commonwealth Sport Movement from athletes seeing they are a part of the decision-making process.
- Enhanced understanding of athletes' needs, protecting against oversights as it relates to the Games, athletes' performances, and the overall well-being of athletes, while also gaining clear insights of possible opportunities.
- Greater diversity of thought contributing to more effective decision-making.
- Athletes improved well-being.
- Athletes improved athletic performances.
- Superior opportunity for athletes to reach their competitive goals and athletic potential.
- Greater feedback from athletes.
- Athletes view their Commonwealth Sport experience as positive and worth promoting the brand and staying involved.
- Conflicts and disputes are resolved fairly.
- Reduction in the use of banned substances.
- Insurance of consistent successful Games, attracting the participation of the world's best athletes within the Commonwealth.
- Increased brand awareness of the CGF and Commonwealth Sport.
- Commonwealth Sport asserts itself as a leader as the first multi-sport organization to fully adopt an athlete-centred principles and actions.
- Athletes remain as participants in the Commonwealth Sport system in some capacity after their competitive careers.
- Establish engaged alumni within Commonwealth Sport with a desire to give back.
- enhances both the individual athlete and contributes to the wider success of the Commonwealth Sport movement. When the athlete is enhanced in a holistic approach, the whole Commonwealth Sport movement benefits.

⁵ Thibault, L., Kihl, L., & Babiak, K. (2010). Democratization and governance in international sport: addressing issues with athlete involvement in organizational policy. *International Journal of Sport Policy*, 2, 275-302.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE CGF

The following are minimum standards, recommended to ensure the adoption of athlete-centred practices by the CGF. *Recommendations have been adapted from AthletesCAN's Minimum Expectations - Athlete-Centredness.*⁶

1. All key committees within the CGF, where program and policy decisions impacting athletes are made, contain 20 percent athlete representation. For example, this may include committees such as the Board of Directors, Sports Committee, and working groups.
2. All athlete representative positions, including the CGF Athletes Advisory Commission Chair, regional athlete representative positions, and all participation of athlete representation on various Commonwealth sport committees and boards are peer elected positions by the athletes.
3. The CGF will promote and facilitate the peer election and participation of athlete representation including the CGF Athletes Advisory Commission Chair, regional athlete representative positions, and CGA athlete representatives.
4. Athlete representatives are directly involved in developing and/or updating policies and procedures which directly affect them. For example, the constitution, the AAC Terms of Reference, athlete agreements, codes of conduct, discipline, grievance/appeals, team selection, health and safety, service levels, budgeting, and other pertinent issues that affect Commonwealth athletes.
5. Elected athlete representatives hold a voting position on boards and committees, demonstrating inclusion in the decision-making process.
6. The CGF includes provision for independent arbitration as an element of its grievance procedures, for use by athletes and other members, for the settlement of disputes which have already exhausted the Commonwealth Sport internal appeals process.
7. Athlete-centredness should be assessed annually by the CGFs and athlete representatives as a means of tracking progression.
8. A commitment from the CGF to work with its athlete representatives, and the AAC to create an athlete-centred work plan, with milestones, resource requirements and timelines identified.

⁶ Adapted from Effective Athlete Leadership (p. 28), by AthletesCAN, 1999. Copyright 1995,1996,1997,1998,1999 by Athletes CAN (Ann Peel).

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE CGAS

The following are minimum standards, recommended to ensure the adoption of athlete-centred practices by the CGAs. *Recommendations have been adapted from AthletesCAN's Minimum Expectations - Athlete-Centredness.*⁷

1. All key committees within the CGAs, where program and policy decisions impacting athletes are made, contain 20 percent athlete representation. For example, this may include committees such as the Board of Directors, Sports Committee, and working groups.
2. All athlete representative positions, including the CGA's athlete representative and all participation of athlete representation on various committees and boards are peer elected positions by the athletes.
3. CGAs will promote and facilitate the peer election and participation of athlete representation including the CGAs athlete representative position(s).
4. Athlete representatives are directly involved in developing and/or updating policies and procedures which directly affect them. For example, the constitution, the Terms of Reference, athlete agreements, codes of conduct, discipline, grievance/appeals, team selection, health and safety, service levels, budgeting, and other pertinent issues that affect Commonwealth athletes.
5. Elected athlete representatives hold a voting position on boards and committees, demonstrating inclusion in the decision-making process.
6. CGAs include provision for independent arbitration as an element of its grievance procedures, for use by athletes and other members, for the settlement of disputes which have already exhausted other internal appeals processes.
7. Athlete-centredness should be assessed annually by CGAs and athlete representatives as a means of tracking progression.
8. A commitment from CGAs to work with its athlete representatives, to create an athlete-centred work plan, with milestones, resource requirements and timelines identified.

⁷ Adapted from Effective Athlete Leadership (p. 28), by AthletesCAN, 1999. Copyright 1995,1996,1997,1998,1999 by Athletes CAN (Ann Peel).

CHECKLIST

The following are a checklist for the CGF, CGAs and all others a member of Commonwealth Sport to use to assess their progress in becoming athlete-centred.⁸

1. Mission, objects, constitutional documents, and goals statements place athletes as the central focus of planning, administration, program design and implementation, and include the following values:
 - a. the athlete is recognized as a whole person and encouraged to flourish, with competitive athletics as an important but only one part of their life experience;
 - b. the athlete's physical health, mental health, and safety are protected;
 - c. athletes' rights and obligations are understood and respected; and
 - d. the infrastructure required to support the development of the athlete is central.
2. The AAC and athlete representatives of Commonwealth Sport are supported by Commonwealth Game Federation and/or their Commonwealth Games Association and are a criterion for continued sport activity, such that:
 - a. they receive support to meet regularly and to communicate with the athletes;
 - b. they are integrated into policy and program development; and
 - c. the AAC and/or athlete representatives designate appropriate athletes for key committees and Boards of Directors.
 - d. Dedicated resource support to realize the AAC strategy
 - e. An integrated CGF paid staff member with a titled role (e.g., Athlete Engagement Manager) employed in a full-time role to assist the AAC and provide support to drive the implementation of strategy
3. Elected athlete representatives are directly involved in developing policies and procedures for:
 - a. the CGF's and CGAs' constitutions;
 - b. Terms of References for athletes' councils, commissions and committees;
 - c. codes of conduct;
 - d. team selection;
 - e. athlete-related service levels;
 - f. health and safety;
 - g. discipline, grievance, and appeal;

⁸ Adapted from Athlete-centred sport. Discussion paper (p. 23-24), by AthletesCAN, 1994. Copyright 1994 by Ann Peel.

- h. harassment; and
 - i. other issues of importance as they arise.
- 4. Elected athlete representatives are fully supported and funded to attend:
 - a. board meetings;
 - b. key commission/committee meetings; and
 - c. other important fora.
- 5. Elected athlete representatives hold a voting position on boards and committees, demonstrating inclusion in the decision-making process.
- 6. Athletes are educated about policies and procedures within the CGF and their respective CGA, external forces affecting them, the national and international sport system, and any changes.
- 7. Athletes are equal partners in determining the content of Athlete-Sport Organization Agreements. Accountability measures are agreed upon and included for both partners.
- 8. Performance goals are mutually agreed upon. Sport leaders avoid placing athletes in situations where they are confronted with externally imposed moral dilemmas, such as the setting of performance goals which cannot be achieved using fair and ethical means. Athletes share this responsibility for striving for excellence within an ethical framework.
- 9. Athlete environments are assessed to ensure holistic development.
- 10. Injury/accident incidence is monitored, analyzed, and measures are taken to ensure prevention.
- 11. Harassment is prevented by educational programs and monitoring. Policies and procedures are in place to deal with harassment, should it occur. Support systems are in place to assist athletes who have been harassed.
- 12. Decisions and reallocation of resources are based on stated priority and values related to the holistic development of athletes.
- 13. Developmental and competitive opportunities exist to help athletes reach their athletic potential.
- 14. Athlete rights are standardized and not CGA or sport-dependent. Internal appeal procedures honour the principles of natural justice, fairness, and no apprehension of bias by having, for instance, notice of hearing and of the case to be met, written decisions, the right to representation, third party decision makers, and the right to appeal to an arbitration board.
- 15. An alternative dispute resolution mechanism is established that operates independently of the sport organizations.
- 16. An Athlete Ombudsperson office is established, and an Athlete Advocate is included in all Games mission complements. An Athlete Advocate provides independent, confidential advice to athletes regarding their rights and responsibilities during a Games, assisting them with possible disputes or complaints, and provide resolution. Additionally, they advocate for equality, fairness and timeliness in the resolution of matters.

CONCLUSION

Athletes are the *raison d'être* of Commonwealth Sport, where they are both the consumer and producer of sport. As such, an athlete-centred Commonwealth Sport benefits all keys stakeholders involved, making it a worthwhile investment. The first step in becoming an athlete-centred sport system begins with the Commonwealth Games Federation adopting this philosophy, which is laudably exemplified in its mission statement of being, “an athlete-centred, sport-focused Commonwealth Sports Movement, with integrity, global impact and embraced by communities.”

The adoption of this “concept,” forms the “process” of being athlete-centred. This involves the CGF, the CGAs, and all members of Commonwealth Sport empowering the AAC and other athlete representatives to shape their pathway. Every CGA needs to have a peer-elected athlete representative, and these representatives need to be trusted by the leaders in sports, that athletes can recognize their needs, provide solutions to problems, and must be included in the decision-making process. Indeed, the voice of athletes should not be silenced or diluted. By so doing, Commonwealth Sport can only benefit. Commonwealth athletes offer unique insights and a rare opportunity to help positively shape the future of Commonwealth Sport.

Key Takeaways

- All key committees within the Commonwealth Sport, where program and policy decisions impacting athletes are made, should contain 20 percent athlete representation.
- All athlete representative positions and all participation of athlete representation on various Commonwealth sport committees and boards should be peer elected positions by the athletes.
- Athlete-representatives should hold voting positions, in adherence to being a part of the decision-making process
- Athlete-centredness within the Commonwealth Sport should be assessed annually